

Statement from the European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAc)
to the European Strategy Preparatory Group (ESPG)

On the Prospect and Vision of Ultra-High Gradient Plasma Accelerators for High Energy Physics

- Update to our 2012 Statement to the ESGP, list of Institutes and Names at the End of Document -

Abstract

Plasma accelerators generate accelerating fields that are up to 1,000 times higher than fundamentally possible in RF accelerators. They therefore offer a promising alternative path to the high-energy frontier. In 2012 the European Strategy Preparatory Group received for the first time detailed input about the prospects and promise of plasma accelerators, a 15 page report provided by the EU-funded European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAc). The network published a 31 page report on a European strategy for plasma accelerators in 2017. Here we provide a short update on the prospect of plasma accelerators for high energy physics. We propose that the next European strategy for particle physics should explicitly list ultra-high gradient plasma acceleration and, if possible, its supporting international projects as essential R&D towards a compact alternative for future colliders.

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December 18th, 2018

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Background:

In 2012 the European Strategy Preparatory Group received for the first time detailed input about the prospects and promise of plasma accelerators [1], a 15 page report provided by the EU-funded European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAC). The 2017 EuroNNAC report on a European strategy (31 pages) is available at [2]. Here we provide a short update and input.

Promise of Plasma Accelerators:

Plasma accelerators generate accelerating fields that are up to 1,000 times higher than fundamentally possible in RF accelerators. Plasma accelerators therefore offer a promising alternative path to the high-energy frontier. Laser pulses, electron or proton bunches (drivers) can excite these ultra-high fields in plasma devices. The three driver technologies are explored in theoretical and experimental programs in- and outside of Europe. Since 2012 laser-driven plasma accelerators have demonstrated beam energies above 8 GeV and bunch charges up to 0.5 nC. Electron-driven plasma accelerators have demonstrated high-efficiency and multi-GeV acceleration of electrons and positrons. Proton-driven plasma accelerators have shown acceleration of electrons by 2 GeV. The progress is rapid, also in supporting technologies like lasers with high peak power (CPA awarded with the 2018 Nobel Prize of Physics) and high average power, plasma sources and plasma lenses.

While there are many tasks still to be handled there is no proven show-stopper in the new plasma technology for reaching high beam energies. Beam quality is now the focus and this can be demonstrated at a few GeV of beam energy with scientific applications like free-electron lasers, fixed target experiments or X ray imaging devices. Ongoing activities towards producing high quality beams with the various driver technologies will serve as a required stepping stone to a plasma linear collider.

New Major Plasma Acceleration Projects since the last European Strategy Update:

Important new projects were funded since the last strategy update in Europe and beyond. These include the Horizon2020 EU Design Study for a “European Research Plasma Accelerator with eXcellence In Applications” **EuPRAXIA** involving 41 institutes [3], the international **AWAKE** experiment [4] at CERN involving 18 institutes and the international **ALEGRO** study [5] on a possible future plasma linear collider. New national activities in Europe since 2012 are the Plasma Wakefield Accelerator Steering Committee (PWASC) in the UK [6], the multi-institutional laser plasma acceleration project ATHENA [7] in the Helmholtz Association in Germany, the ELBE center at HZDR, CILEX in France, CLARA and SCAPA in the UK, EuPRAXIA@SPARC_LAB at INFN-LNF in Italy [8], Lund in Sweden, JuSPARC at FZJ and FLASHForward and SINBAD at DESY. There are strong activities with new funding on plasma acceleration in Japan (ImPACT), in China (Synergetic Extreme Condition User Facility SECUF) and in the US (FACET-II, BELLA).

Our Proposal for the Strategy Update:

The next European strategy for particle physics should **explicitly list ultra-high gradient plasma acceleration** and, if possible, its supporting international projects (see above in bold) **as essential R&D towards a compact alternative for future colliders**.

References

- [1] 2012 Statement to ESPG from EuroNNAc on Plasma Acceleration, edited by R. Assmann (CERN), A. Caldwell (MPI), M. Ferrario (INFN), J. Osterhoff (DESY), T. Tajima (LMU), H. Videau (Ecole Polytechnique), <https://cds.cern.ch/record/1560093>
- [2] Final EuroNNAc2 report in the EuCARD2 project: "A European Roadmap", published as EU deliverable report 15.6.2017, https://edms.cern.ch/ui/file/1325207/2/EuCARD2_Del7-2-Final.pdf
- [3] Horizon2020 EU Design Study for a European Research Plasma Accelerator with eXcellence In Applications (EuPRAXIA), coordinated by DESY (R. Assmann et al), a consortium of 41 institutes, <http://www.eupraxia-project.eu>
- [4] Advanced Wakefield Experiment at CERN (AWAKE), a collaboration of 18 institutes (A. Caldwell, MPP, M. Wing, UCL, E. Gschwendtner, CERN, P. Muggli, MMP, K. Lotov, BINP et al), <https://awake.web.cern.ch>
- [5] Advanced LinEar collider study GROup (ALEGRO): An international study group to promote Advanced and Novel Accelerators for High Energy Physics applications. Sponsored by ICFA (B. Cros et al), <http://www.lpgp.u-psud.fr/icfaana/alegro>
- [6] Plasma Wakefield Accelerator Steering Committee (PWASC) in the UK, coordinated by S. Hooker, B. Hidding et al, <http://pwasc.org.uk>
- [7] Accelerator Technology HELmholtz iNfrAstructure (ATHENA), project on laser-driven plasma acceleration by DESY, FZJ, GSI mit HI Jena, HZB, HZDR, KIT, coordinated by R. Assmann, U. Schramm et al, <https://www.athena-helmholtz.de>
- [8] M. Ferrario et al., "EuPRAXIA@SPARC_LAB Design study towards a compact FEL facility at LNF", Nucl. Instr. and Meth. A, Vol. 909, p. 134

Signed by the following EuroNNAc3 institutional representatives (in alphabetical order of first representative)

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The European Network for Novel Accelerators (EuroNNAc) is part of the EU-funded project ARIES and includes representatives from the following research institutes as members:

Beijing National Laboratory (IOP-CAS), Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL), Budker Institute of Nuclear Physics (BINP), Center for the Advancement of Natural Discoveries using Light Emission (CANDLE), Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives (CEA), Centre National de la Recherche Sci-

entifique (CNRS), CERN, The National Institute of Optics (CNR-INO), Cockroft Institute, Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY), Ecole Polytechnique, Eindhoven University of Technology, ELI Beamlines, ENSTA Paris Tech, Ferdinand Braun Institut (FBH), Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory (FNAL), Forschungszentrum Jülich, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Institut national de physique nucléaire et de physique des particules (IN2P3), INFN Frascati, INFN LNF, INFN Milano, INFN Roma1, Institute of Applied Physics of the Russian Academy of Sciences (IAPRAS), Institute of Physics Chinese Academy, Instituto Superior Tecnico de Lisboa (IST-ID), John Adams Institute at Imperial College (JAI), Joint Institute for High Temperatures of Russian Academy of Sciences (JIHT), High Energy Accelerator Research Organization (KEK), KFKI/Wigner Research Centre for Physics, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Laboratory of the Linear Accelerator (LAL), Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory (LBNL), Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL), Laboratoire de Physique des Gaz et des Plasmas (LPGP), Laboratoire d'Utilisation des Lasers Intenses (LULI), Lund University, Osaka University, Oxford University, Paul Scherrer Institut, PHLAM Université de Lille, Queen's University of Belfast, RIKEN SPring-8, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory (SLAC), Synchrotron SOLEIL, STFC Central Laser Facility (CLF), STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL), Stony Brook University, Tsinghua University, TU Darmstadt, University of California Los Angeles (UCLA), University College London, University of Bern, University of Düsseldorf, University of Jena, University of Liverpool, University of München and Max Planck Institutes, University of Oslo, University of Pisa, University of Rome Sapienza, University of Rome Tor Vergata, University of Strathclyde